

Ethnobotanical Appraisal of Medicinal Plants Used by Inhabitants of Narsipatnam Division, Visakhapatnam District, Andhra Pradesh

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Suggested Citation

Venumadhav, R., Ikkurthi, V., Skylab, G., & Mallikarjuna, K. (2024). Ethnobotanical Appraisal of Medicinal Plants Used by Inhabitants of Narsipatnam Division, Visakhapatnam District, Andhra Pradesh. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 2(5), 474-497.
DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2024.2\(5\).48](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2024.2(5).48)

Abstract:

The preliminary investigations of Ethnobotanical appraisal of Medicinal plants used by Inhabitants of Narsipatnam Division, Visakhapatnam District, Andhra Pradesh with their recipes, preparation of drugs, administration, and usage from several centuries. Therapeutic uses of some of the species given in the table were cross checked with alternative ethno botanical systems viz. Ayurveda, Unani, Sidha and Homeopathy. One hundred and fifty-six (156) crude drugs (species) belonging to one hundred and thirty-two (132) genera and sixty-nine (69) families were collected based on folk-lore knowledge. The pattern of the plant uses as per habitat (terrestrial, aquatic/epiphytes), habit (growth form), plant part (tissue) and taxonomic category (Systematically families), nativity and occurrence (wild/cultivated) were established. Of the 156 crude drugs wild and naturalized species, 61 are trees, 36 are shrubs, 29 are herbs, 28 are climbers and remaining each one is liana and parasites. (Appendix_1).

Keywords: *Crude drug, primary report, Vizag.*

Introduction

Andhra Pradesh's North Eastern Coastal districts, Narsipatnam Division, Visakhapatnam district is located between 170 – 15' and 180– 32' in Northern latitude and between 180 – 54' and 830 – 30' in Eastern longitude. Its borders are as follows: East Godavari District borders it on the south, Orissa State borders it on the west, and the Bay of Bengal borders it on the east (**Fig -1**).

On the north, it is partially surrounded by Orissa State and Vizianagaram District.

The present study is conducted with Narsipatnam Division agency with 3 Mandalas (Chintha palli, Gudem kotha veedi and Koyyuru) inhabited by tribal people. The tribes in this region are Bagata, Kutuya, Nukkadora, Gadaba and Valmiki tribes. Demarcation of reserve forests near settlements is a source of conflict between the tribes and the forest administration.

The group uses the forest for non-timber products, wood, construction materials, herbs,

water and aquaculture, as well as agriculture, hunting and charcoal production.

Figure 1. View of Map- Showing 3 Mandals in Srikakulam District

Figure 2. Investigator – Interact with Tribal Gurus (Expert in Ethnomedicine)

Materials and Methods

During study of Medicinal Plants Used by Inhabitants of Narsipatnam Division agency with 3 Mandalas (Chintha palli, Gudem kotha veedi and Koyyuru) inhabited by tribal people. The tribes in this region are Bagata, Kutiya, Nukkadora, Gadaba and Valmiki tribes. various field trips were conducted and were vouched from various natural populations during the period 2020-2023. Collected Ethno Botanical Data and Plants specimens collected flowering or fruiting Seasons. Specimens critically observed and identified, *herbarium* specimens deposited at The University of Acharya Nagarjuna University (ANU) was done. Perusal of *related published literature* (Amarasingham et. al. (1964), Chabra et al. (1984), Chadwick and Marsh (1994), Chopra et al. (1956), Das and Bhattachargee (1970), Gamble (1953), Gibbs (1974), Harborne (1984), Hema and Yosodamma (2008), Hooker (1984), Jadhav and Reddy (2006), Jain (1964), Jain (1981), Kirtikar and Boser (1933), Murthy et al. (2007), Nadkarni (1976), Nazaneen & Shali (2008), Pullaiah et al. (2003), Pullaiah and Yasodamma (1989), Raju et al. (2008), Rao et al. (2005), Rao et al. (2006), Rathnam and Raju (2005), Reddy et al. (1986), Reddy & Raju (2002), Reddy and Sujatha (2002), Santaram (1983), Sheriff (2005), Venumadhav et al. (2022)., for the taxonomic confirmation. Updated nomenclature, distribution along with field photographs has been presented. All Field data noted carefully field note books, each drug material individually recorded videos and photographs taken with GIS tags.

Results and Discussion

The preliminary investigations of Ethnobotanical appraisal of Medicinal plants used by Inhabitants of Narsipatnam Division, Visakhapatnam District, Andhra Pradesh with their recipes, preparation of drugs, administration, and usage from several centuries. Therapeutic uses of some of the species given in the table were cross checked with alternative ethno botanical systems viz. Ayurveda, Unani,

Sidha and Homeopathy. One hundred and fifty-six (156) crude drugs (species) belonging to one hundred and thirty-two (132) genera and sixty-nine (69) families were collected based on folklore knowledge. The pattern of the plant uses as per habitat (terrestrial, aquatic/epiphytes), habit (growth form), plant part (tissue) and taxonomic category (Systematically families), nativity and occurrence (wild/cultivated) were established. Of the 156 crude drugs wild and naturalized species, 61 are trees, 36 are shrubs, 29 are herbs, 28 are climbers and remaining each one are Liana and parasites.

Conclusion

The preliminary investigations of Ethnobotanical appraisal of Medicinal plants used by Inhabitants of Narsipatnam Division, Visakhapatnam District, Andhra Pradesh following species *Abrus precatorius* traditional uses, caution is necessary due to the plant's toxicity, particularly the seeds, which should never be ingested or handled without care. *Abutilon indicum*, commonly known as Indian mallow or Atibala, is a medicinal plant widely used in traditional systems of medicine like Ayurveda, Unani, and Siddha. Traditionally used to treat conditions like coughs, asthma, and bronchitis. Decoctions made from the leaves and roots are believed to have expectorant and demulcent properties. Despite its extensive use in traditional medicine, like many herbal remedies, its use should be approached with caution and ideally under the guidance of a trained practitioner. *Alangium salvifolium*, commonly known as sage-leaved *alangium* or anjan, is a medicinal plant used in traditional systems such as Ayurveda, Unani, and Siddha. It is valued for its various therapeutic properties. In some cultures, parts of the tree are used in religious rituals and offerings. Though *Alangium salvifolium* is widely used in traditional medicine, it should be used with caution, and guidance from a knowledgeable herbalist or healthcare practitioner is recommended, especially for internal use. *Andrographis paniculata*, commonly known as kalmegh, green chiretta, or the king of

bitters, is a highly valued medicinal herb in Ayurveda, Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM), and other systems of traditional medicine. It is known for its bitter taste and wide range of therapeutic uses. While *Andrographis paniculata* is generally considered safe in therapeutic doses, excessive use or long-term use should be done under the supervision of a healthcare practitioner, especially for individuals with underlying health conditions. *Cissampelos pareira*, commonly known as velvetleaf, abuta, or patha, is a medicinal plant traditionally used in Ayurveda, Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM), and South American herbal practices. It is valued for its various pharmacological properties. In n Ayurvedic medicine, *Cissampelos pareira* is known as Patha and is used to treat various ailments such as fevers, diarrhea, urinary tract infections, and menstrual disorders. It is classified as a cooling herb and is used to pacify the pitta dosha (heat). *Mitragyna parviflora*, also known as Kaim, Kaimba, or Kadamb, is a medicinal plant related to the *Mitragyna* genus, which includes *Mitragyna speciosa* (kratom). However, *Mitragyna parviflora* is distinct and has its own traditional medicinal uses, particularly in Ayurveda and folk medicine. The Jatapu, Kammara, Manne Dora, Konda

Doras, Malis, Mukha Dora, Savaras, Gadaba Tribes and Valmiki tribes possessing rich folklore information forms the prime source and exists scope to extend scientific research in further isolation and characterization of active principles involved in the pharmacological utility. Keeping because the fact potential source of medicinal plants of folklore origin needs to be preserved and conserved. Sacred groves are the site of ritual and secret society initiations, a local where social and political values, morals, secrets, and laws are passed on to the younger generations. There is small information on the ways in which these values are changing. No studies explore the implications of changing cultural values on forest resource use. The ethnobotanical appraisal reveals a profound connection between the tribes and their medicinal plants, highlighting the importance of these species in traditional health practices. The findings underscore the need for conservation efforts and the potential for further research to support the preservation of this invaluable knowledge and biodiversity. Future initiatives should focus on integrating traditional practices with modern conservation strategies to safeguard these resources for future generations.

Figure 3. Systematic Enumeration

Figure 4. Life form Analysis

Acknowledgements

The authors are thankful to the notified and de notified Adivasis groups, their v aids, ojhas, bhopas etc. and forest officials who provided valuable information on this subject, first author greatly acknowledges Department of Botany, Acharya Nagarjuna University (ANU) for providing lab facilities during the Research work, in Guntur. authors are also thankful to the Ministry of Environment, Forests, and Climate Change for facilities and to the Department of Environment and Forests, Andhra Pradesh, for necessary permission and logistic support during field studies.

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Appendix

S. No.	Botanical Name	Family	Vernacular Name	Habit	Ailment	Parts	Mode of uses
1	<i>Abrus precatorius</i>	Fabaceae	Guruvinda	Climber	Abortion	Root	Decoction
					Contraceptive	seed	Powder
					Leucoderma	Leaf	Paste
					Ring worm	Leaf	Paste
					Snake bite	seed	Powder
2	<i>Abutilon indicum</i>	Malvaceae	Tuttura benda	Shrub	Dysentery	Leaf	Paste
					Galactagogue	Root	Paste
					Scabies	Seed	Paste
3	<i>Acacia leucophloea</i>	Mimosaceae	Tella thumma	Tree	Tooth ache	Stem bark	Decoction
					Wounds	Stem bark	Paste
4	<i>Acacia nilotica</i>	Mimosaceae	Nalla tumma'	Tree	Diarrhoea	Stem bark	Decoction
					Leucoderma	Leaf	Paste
					Leucorrhoea	Gum	Paste
5	<i>Acacia torta</i>	Mimosaceae	Korintha	Shrub	Whooping cough	Root Bark	Paste
					Wounds	Stem bark	Paste
6	<i>Agave cantala</i>	Agavaceae	Kitha Nara'	Shrub	Bruises	Leaf	Juice
					Purgatives	Leaf	paste
7	<i>Ailanthus excelsa</i>	Simaroubaceae	Pedda manu'	Tree	Dysentery in poultry	Stem bark	Powder
					Epilepsy	Stem bark	Powder
8	<i>Alangium salvifolium</i>	Alangiaceae	Uduga	Shrub	Bone fracture	Root	Paste
					Constipation	Root Bark	Powder
					Fever	Root	Decotion
					Leucorrhoea	Stem bark	Decotion
					Rheumatoid arthritis	Leaf	Paste
					Syphilis	Root	Powder
9	<i>Alstonia scholaris</i>	Apocyanaceae	Edakula pala	Tree	Malaria	Stem bark	Decoction
10	<i>Alstonia venenata</i>	Apocyanaceae	Edakula pala	Tree	Anthelmintic	Stem bark	Decoction
					Stomach pain	Stem bark	Paste
					Syphilis	Fruit	Paste

11	<i>Ampelocissus latifolia</i>	Vitaceae	Adavi draksha	Climber	Boils and Wounds	Leaf	Paste
					Ringworm	Root	Paste
12	<i>Anamirta cocculus</i>	Menispermaceae	Koditeega	Climber	Contraction of uterus	Leaf	Paste
13	<i>Andrographis paniculata</i>	Acanthaceae	Nela vemu	Herb	Boils and Blisters	Leaf	Paste
					Cholera	Leaf	Paste
					Diarrhoea	Leaf	Paste
					Jaundice	Leaf	Decoction
					Leprosy	Leaf	Paste
					Leucorrhoea	Leaf	Paste
					Malaria	Leaf	Paste
					Rheumatoid arthritis	Leaf	Paste
					Scabies	Leaf	Paste
					Small pox	Root	Paste
					Snake bite	Whole	Paste
14	<i>Aristolochia bracteolata</i>	Artislochiaceae	Gadida gadapa	Herb	Eczema	Leaf	Juice
					Cuts and wounds	Leaf	Paste
					Leucorrhoea	Stem	Juice
					Snake bite	Leaf	Paste
15	<i>Asparagus recemosus</i>	Asparagaceae	Pillitegalu	Climber	Bronchitis	Root	Paste
					Diabetes	Root	Powder
					Tumours	Root	Powder
					Wounds	Root	Paste
16	<i>Atalantia monophylla</i>	Rutaceae	Karu nimma	Shrub	Rheumatoid arthritis	Fruit	Juice
					Scabies	Root Bark	Paste
					Scorpion sting	Leaf	Paste
17	<i>Atylosia scarabaeoides</i>	Fabaceae	Adavi ulava teega	Climber	Menorrhagia	Root	Paste
18	<i>Blumea axillaris</i>	Asteraceae	Kukka pugaku'	Herb	Cooling effect	Leaf	Paste
					Jaundice	Leaf	Juice
					Skin diseases	Leaf	Paste
19	<i>Bombax ceiba</i>	Bombacaceae	Mulla buruga'	Tree	Boils and Sores	Flower	Paste

					Pimples and complexion	Stem	Paste
20	<i>Boswellia serrata</i>	Burseraceae	Guggilam	Tree	Insect repellent	Stem	Powder
					Scrofula	Stem bark	Paste
					Diarrhoea	Stem bark	Paste
					Chronic ulcers	Resin	Paste
21	<i>Butea monosperma</i>	Fabaceae	Moduga	Tree	Abdominal disorders	Stem	Powder
					Backache	Flower	Paste
					Menorrhagia	Stem bark	Paste
22	<i>Caesalpinia bonduc</i>	Caesalpinaceae	Gachakaya	Shrub	Epilepsy	Root Bark	Pills
					Abortion	Seeds	Powder
					Helminthiasis	Leaf	Paste
					Obesity	Seed	Paste
					Abdominal colic	Root	Powder
23	<i>Calotropis gigantea</i>	Asclepiadaceae	Tella jilledu'	Shrub	Abortion	Leaf	Paste
					Asthma	Flower	Paste
					skin diseases	Leaf	Paste
					Fertility	Root	Powder
					Filariasis	Seed	Paste
					Menorrhagia	Latex	Milk
					Oedema	Leaf	Paste
					Scorpion sting	Latex	Milk
24	<i>Careya arborea</i>	Lecythidaceae	Gummodu cchettu	Tree	Body swelling	Bark	Paste
25	<i>Caryota urens</i>	Arecaceae	Jeeluga	Tree	Dyspepsia	Inflorescence	Sap
					Tympanites	Leaf	Powder
26	<i>Senna auriculata</i>	Caesalpinaceae	Thangedu	Shrub	Diabetic ulcers	Whole Plant	Powder
					Burns	Leaf	Powder
					Bone fracture	Leaf	Paste
					Dysuria	Stem bark	Paste
					Intermittent fever	Leaf	Decoction
					Leucorrhoea	Root	Decoction

					Night blindness	Leaf	Juice
					Ophthalmic diseases	Leaf	Paste
					Snake bite	Leaf	Paste
					Ulcers in mouth	Leaf	Paste
27	<i>Casearia elliptica</i>	Flacourtiaceae	Chilaka duddi	Tree	Leprosy	Leaf	Decoction
28	<i>Cassia fistula</i>	Caesalpiniaceae	Rella	Tree	Body pains	Stem bark	Paste
					Cuts	Fruit	Juice
					Dyspepsia	Fruit	Juice
					Dysuria	Flower	Paste
					Fever	Stem bark	Decoction
					Leprosy	Leaf	Paste
					Urinary troubles	Stem bark	Decoction
					Constipation	Fruit	Pulp
					Intestinal worms	Flowers	Paste
29	<i>Senna hirsuta</i>	Caesalpiniaceae	Tagara	Shrub	Hair oil	Seed	Oil
30	<i>Senna occidentalis</i>	Caesalpiniaceae	Kasinthā		Paralysis	Root	Paste
					Bone fracture	Leaf	Paste
					Carbuncle	Leaf	Paste
					Typhoid	Root	Paste
					Honeybee bite	Leaf	Juice
					Leucoderma	Leaf	Paste
					Ring worm	Leaf	Juice
31	<i>Senna tora</i>	Caesalpiniaceae	Tantemu	Shrub	Dandruff	Seed	Paste
					skin diseases	Leaf	Paste
					Fever	Leaf	Juice
					Honeybee bite	Leaf	Paste
					Ring worm	Root	Paste
					Tumours	Seed	Paste
32	<i>Cassytha filiformis</i>	Lauraceae	Seethamma savaralu'	Climber	Leucorrhoea	Stem	Juice

					Muscle pain	Stem	Paste
33	<i>Catunaregam spinosa</i>	Rubiaceae	Manga chettu'	Tree	Abortion	Stem bark	Paste
					Fever	Root	Paste
					Bone pains	Stem	Paste
34	<i>Celastrus paniculatus</i>	Celastraceae	Jyotishmati	Climber	Abortion	Stem bark	Paste
					Carbuncle	Seed	Oil
					Rheumatoid arthritis	seed	Oil
					Wounds	Leaf	Paste
35	<i>Centella asiatica</i>	Apiaceae	Saraswathi aku'	Herb	Blood purification	Leaf	Decoction
					Diarrhoea	Whole Plant	Powder
					Memory power	Leaf	Powder
					Leprosy	Leaf	Decoction
					Pimples	Leaf	Paste
36	<i>Chloroxylon swietenia</i>	Rutaceae	Billakarra	Tree	Impotency	Root bark	Decoction
					Mosquito repellent	Leaf	Decoction
					Scorpion sting	Stem bark	Paste
					Urinary disorders	Gum	Paste
37	<i>Cissampelos pareira</i>	Menispermaceae	Adavibank a teega'	Climber	Cuts and wounds	Root	Paste
					Snake bite	Root	Paste
					Chest pain	Stem	Paste
					Stomach pain	Leaf	Decoction
38	<i>Cissus quadrangularis</i>	Vitaceae	Nalleru	Climber	Loss of appetite	Stem	Powder
39	<i>Cissus vitiginea</i>	Vitaceae	Adavi Draksha teega	Climber	Scabies	Leaf	Paste
40	<i>Cleistanthus collinus</i>	Uphorbiaceae	Kodisa	Tree	Insect repellent	Leaf	Powder
					Rheumatoid arthritis	Root Bark	Paste
41	<i>Cleome viscosa</i>	Cleomaceae	Kukka vaminta'	Herb	Cuts and Wounds	Leaf	Paste
					Earache	Leaf	Juice
					Toothache	Leaf	Juice

42	<i>Rotheba serrata</i>	Verbenaceae	Bommala marri'	Shrub	Asthma	Root	Decoction
					Insect repellent	Leaf	Powder
43	<i>Clitoria ternatea</i>	Fabaceae	Shanku pushpi'	Climber	Antiemetics	Root	Juice
					Brain tonic	Seed	Powder
					Centipede bite	Leaf	Paste
					Oedema	Leaf	Juice
					Rheumatism	Root	Paste
44	<i>Cocculus birsutus</i>	Menispermaceae	Dusara teega'	Climber	Diabetes	Leaf	Paste
45	<i>Coldenia procumbens</i>	Boraginaceae	Hamsapadu	Herb	Cuts and wounds	Whole Plant	Powder
					Muscle pain	Leaf	Paste
					Ulcers	Leaf	Juice
46	<i>Commiphora caudata</i>	Burseraceae	Adavi mamidi'	Tree	Asthma	Whole Plant	Decoction
					Cold and Cough	Stem bark	Powder
					Fever	Gum	Smoke
					Pneumonia	Gum	Smoke
					Obesity	Whole Plant	Decoction
					Ulcers in stomach	Stem bark	Paste
47	<i>Crotalaria retusa</i>	Fabaceae	Naga giligicha'	Shrub	Chicken pox	Root	Paste
48	<i>Crotalaria verrucosa</i>	Fabaceae	Giligitcha kaya'	Shrub	Scabies	Leaf	Paste
					Scorpion sting	Root	Paste
					Snake bite	Root	Paste
49	<i>Curculigo orchioides</i>	Hypoxidaceae	Nela tadi'	Herb	Jaundice	Rhizome	Decoction
					Ophthalmic diseases	Rhizome	Paste
50	<i>Curcuma pseudomontana</i>	Zingiberaceae	Adavi pasupu'	Herb	Anasarca	Rhizome	Paste
					Cooling effect	Rhizome	Decoction
51	<i>Dalbergia latifolia</i>	Fabaceae	Irugudu cheva	Tree	skin diseases	Stem bark	Paste

					Oedema	Root bark	Juice
					Rheumatoid arthritis	Stem bark	Juice
52	<i>Decalepis hamiltonii</i>	Asclepiadaceae	Maredu gaddalu'	Climber	Bronchitis	Root	Juice
					Hemorrhage	Root	Paste
53	<i>Dendrophthoe falcata</i>	Loranthaceae	Badhanica	Parasite	Menstrual pain	Root	Decoction
54	<i>Dichrostachys cinerea</i>	Mimosaceae	Veluthuru chettu'	Shrub	Skin diseases	Leaf	Paste
					Rheumatism	Root	Paste
					Fractured bones	Root bark	Paste
					Paralysis	Leaf	Paste
55	<i>Dioscorea bulbifera</i>	Discoreaceae	Adavi dumpa'	Climber	Dyspepsia	Leaf	Juice
					Centipede bite	Root	Paste
56	<i>Dioscorea oppositifolia</i>	Discoreaceae	Tella gadda'	Climber	Cuts and Wounds	Leaf	Paste
57	<i>Dioscorea pentaphylla</i>	Discoreaceae	Dukka pendalam'	Climber	Insecticide	Tuber	Powder
					Rheumatism	Tuber	Paste
58	<i>Diospyros melanoxylon</i>	Ebenaceae	Beedi aku'	Tree	Joint pains	Stem bark	Paste
59	<i>Diospyros sylvatica</i>	Ebenaceae	Nallagatha	Tree	Fits	Stem bark	Paste
60	<i>Dodonaea viscosa</i>	Sapindaceae	Bandadi	Shrub	Muscle pain	Stem bark	Decoction
					Epilepsy	Leaf	Juice
61	<i>Ehretia microphylla</i>	Boraginaceae	Nunemunt ha	Shrub	Ulcers and Wounds	Stem bark	Powder
					Debilis and syphilis	Root	Paste
					Stomach problems	Leaf	Decotion
62	<i>Elephantopus scaber</i>	Asteraceae	Eddunaluk a aaku'	Herb	Cough and Vomiting	Root	Decotion
					Dysentery	Root	Decotion
63	<i>Elytraria acanlis</i>	Acanthaceae	Adugu tappeta'	Herb	Intestinal worms	Root	Powder

					Hydrocele	Leaf	Paste
					Rheumatoid arthritis	Leaf	Paste
					Anasarca	Tuber	Decoction
					Boils	Leaf	Paste
					Menstrual disorders	Leaf	Juice
64	<i>Entada rheedii</i>	Mimosaceae	Gillakaya	Liane	Helminthiasis	Seed	Powder
65	<i>Erythroxylum monogynum</i>	Erythroxylaceae	Pagadam chettu	Shrub	Jaundice	Leaf	Juice
					Helminthiasis	Leaf	Decoction
66	<i>Ficus religiosa</i>	Moraceae	Ravi chettu	Tree	Bed sores	Stem bark	Paste
					Bone fracture	Stem bark	Paste
					Breast cancer	Stem bark	Juice
67	<i>Gloriosa superba</i>	Liliaceae	Adavinaabhi	Herb	Abortion	Root	Paste
					Chicken pox	Tubers	Paste
					Contraceptives	Tubers	Paste
					Leprosy	Tubers	Paste
68	<i>Glycosmis mauritiana</i>	Rutaceae	Golugu	Shrub	Fever	Root	Decoction
					Anemia	Root bark	Powder
					Cough	Root bark	Paste
					Cuts and wounds	Leaf	Paste
					Eczema	Root bark	Paste
69	<i>Gmelina arborea</i>	Verbenaceae	Gummuudu	Tree	Fractures	Stem bark	Paste
					Gonorrhoea	Leaf	Juice
					Malaria	Stem bark	Paste
70	<i>Guazuma ulmifolia</i>	Sterculiaceae	Rudraksha	Tree	Filariasis	Stem bark	Paste
71	<i>Gymnema sylvestre</i>	Asclepiadaceae	Podapatri	Climber	Snake bite	Root	Paste
					Gonorrhoea	Leaf	Powder
72	<i>Haldina cordifolia</i>	Rubiaceae	Bandaru	Tree	Amenorrhoea	Leaf	Paste
					Fever	Leaf	Paste
					Menstrual disorders	Bark	Paste
73	<i>Helicteres isora</i>	Sterculiaceae	Nuli thada'	Shrub	Asthma	Fruit	Paste

74	<i>Hemidesmus indicus</i>	Periplocaceae	Sugandhipala	Climber	skin diseases	Root	Decoction
					Cough	Root	Decoction
					Fever	Root	Decoction
					Rheumatism	Root	Powder
75	<i>Holarrhena pubescens</i>	Apocynaceae	Kodisa paala	Shrub	Cough	Stem	Decoction
					Dysentery	Stem bark	Paste
76	<i>Holoptelea integrifolia</i>	Ulmaceae	Nemalichka	Tree	Rheumatism	Stem bark	Paste
					Ring worm	Leaf	Paste
77	<i>Hymenodictyon orixense</i>	Rubiaceae	Duddipa	Tree	Cuts and wounds	Stem	Paste
78	<i>Ichnocarpus frutescens</i>	Apocynaceae	Pala teega'	Shrub	Hemorrhage	Root	Paste
79	<i>Kalanchoe laciniata</i>	Crassulaceae	Kondakalli	Herb	Bone Fracture	Leaf	Paste
					Carbuncle	Leaf	Paste
80	<i>Leonotis nepetifolia</i>	Lamiaceae	Rana bheri	Shrub	Skin diseases	Whole Plant	Paste
81	<i>Litsea deccanensis</i>	Luraceae	Narra mamidi	Tree	Boils	Stem bark	Paste
					Body pains	Stem bark	Paste
					Cuts	Bark	Paste
82	<i>Litsea glutinosa</i>	Lauraceae	Narra lagi	Tree	Paralysis	Stem bark	Powder
					Snake bite	Stem bark	Paste
83	<i>Madhuca longifolia</i>	Sapotaceae	Ippa	Tree	Stomach pains	Root	Paste
84	<i>Manilkara hexandra</i>	Sapotaceae	Pala karra	Tree	Eyesight	Root	Paste
					Piles	Stem bark	Paste
85	<i>Melia azedarach</i>	Meliaceae	Turaka vepa	Tree	Helminthiasis	Leaf	Paste
					Rheumatism	Stem bark	Powder
86	<i>Merremia tridentata</i>	Convolvulaceae	Seethamma jada	Herb	Hemorrhoids	Whole Plant	Paste
87	<i>Mimosa pudica</i>	Mimosaceae	Atti patti	Herb	Cuts	Whole Plant	Paste
					Diabetes	Leaf	Powder
					Fever	Root	Decoction
					Filariasis	Leaf	Paste
					Menorrhagia	Leaf	Juice
88	<i>Mitragyna parviflora</i>	Rubiaceae	Battaganapa	Tree	Jaundice	Leaf	Juice

					Stomach problems	Bark	Decoction
89	<i>Morinda pubescens</i>	Rubiaceae	Togaru	Tree	Fever	Root	Powder
					Wounds	Leaf	Paste
90	<i>Mucuna pruriens</i>	Fabaceae	Pedda dulagondi	Climber	Aphrodisiac	Seed	Paste
					Nerving tonic	Root	Powder
91	<i>Murraya koenigii</i>	Rutaceae	Karive paku	Shrub	Diarrhea	Leaf	Juice
					Stomach pain	Leaf	Decoction
92	<i>Musa rosacea</i>	Musaceae	Adavi arati	Herb	Dysentery	Rhizome	Juice
					Abortion	Leaf	Sap
93	<i>Naringi crenulata</i>	Rutaceae	Torri velaga'	Tree	Dysentery	Stem bark	Decoction
94	<i>Opuntia dillenii</i>	Cactaceae	Bonthajem udu		Cough	Stem	Latex
					Mumps	Stem	Paste
95	<i>Oroxylum indicum</i>	Bignoniaceae	Pampini	Tree	Epilepsy	Stem bark	Decoction
					Jaundice	Stem bark	Decoction
96	<i>Pachygone ovata</i>	Menispermaceae	Pedda Dusari teega	Climber	Diarrhoea	Root	Decoction
97	<i>Pandanus odoratissimus</i>	Pandanaceae	Mogali	Shrub	skin diseases	Leaf	Paste
98	<i>Pavetta indica</i>	Rubiaceae	Papidi	Tree	Ulcers	Leaf	Paste
					Boils	Leaf	Paste
					Jaundice	Root	Powder
99	<i>Pavonia zeylanica</i>	Malvaceae	Karu benda	Herb	Ring worm	Whole Plant	Paste
100	<i>Petalium murex</i>	Pedaliaceae	Pedda palleru	Herb	Fertility	Fruit	Powder
101	<i>Peltophorum pterocarpum</i>	Caesalpiniaceae	Adavi chintha	Tree	Dysentery	Stem bark	Paste
					Sores	Stem bark	Paste
102	<i>Pergularia daemia</i>	Asclepiadaceae	Dushtaput eega	Shrub	Cough	Leaf	Juice
					Indigestion	Leaf	Juice
					Rheumatic swelling	Leaf	Juice
103	<i>Phoenix sylvestris</i>	Arecaceae	Eetha chettu	Tree	Burning Sensation	Leaf	Paste

104	<i>Phyllanthus amarus</i>	Euphorbiaceae	Nela usiri'	Herb	Dysentery	Whole Plant	Decoction
					Jaundice	Leaf	Powder
					Scorpion-Sting	Whole Plant	Paste
					Ulcers in stomach	Whole Plant	Paste
105	<i>Phyllanthus emblica</i>	Euphorbiaceae	Pedda usiri	Tree	Antibiotic	Fruit	Juice
					Epilepsy	Fruit	Juice
					Hair tonic	Fruit	Juice
106	<i>Piper longum</i>	Piperaceae	Pippallu	Shrub	Cold	Fruit	Powder
					Purgatives	Root	Powder
					Tooth ache	Root	Paste
107	<i>Piper nigrum</i>	Piperaceae	Miriyalu	Climber	Cold and cough	Leaf	Juice
					Dysentery	Root	Decoction
					Toothache	Root	Paste
108	<i>Pithecellobium dulce</i>	Mimosaceae	Seema chintha	Tree	Dysentery	Root bark	Decoction
109	<i>Plumbago indica</i>	Plumbaginaceae	Yerra chitramulam	Shrub	Cough	Root	Decoction
					Backache	Root	Paste
					Paralysis	Root	Paste
110	<i>Plumbago zeylanica</i>	Plumbaginaceae	Tella chitramulam	Shrub	Abortion	Root	Paste
					Malarial fevers	Root	Decoction
					Backache	Stem	Paste
111	<i>Pouzolzia zeylanica</i>	Urticaceae	Eddhu muthe dumpa'	Herb	Boils	Leaf	Paste
					Snake bite	Tuber	Paste
					Ulcers in stomach	Leaf	Paste
112	<i>Prosopis cineraria</i>	Mimosaceae	Jammi	Tree	Leucorrhoea	Leaf	Juice
113	<i>Pterocarpus marsupium</i>	Fabaceae	Yegisa	Tree	Boils and Sores	Leaf	Paste
					Diabetes	Stem bark	Paste
					Toothache	Wood	Paste
					Wounds	Gum	Paste

114	<i>Pterospermum xylocarpum</i>	Sterculiaceae	Lolugu	Tree	Body pains	Stem bark	Paste
115	<i>Pueraria tuberosa</i>	Fabaceae	Nela gummadi	Climber	Galactagogue	Root	Paste
					Ulcers in stomach	Root	Paste
116	<i>Rauwolfia serpentina</i>	Apocyanaceae	Sarpagandhi	Shrub	Blood pressure	Root	Pills
					Dysentery	Whole Plant	Paste
					Dyspepsia	Root	Paste
					Gonorrhoea	Root	Paste
					Leucorrhoea	Stem bark	Powder
					Menstrual disorders	Root	Powder
					Rat bite	Root	Paste
					Snake bite	Root	Paste
117	<i>Santalum album</i>	Santalaceae	Sri gandham	Tree	Headache	Stem	Paste
					Wounds	Stem	Paste
118	<i>Semecarpus anacardium</i>	Anacardiaceae	Nalla jeedi	Tree	Menstrual disorders	Fruit	Paste
119	<i>Sida acuta</i>	Malvaceae	Maha bala	Herb	Nervous weakness	Whole Plant	Powder
120	<i>Sida cordata</i>	Malvaceae	Gayapu aaku	Shrub	Paralysis	Leaf	Juice
					Dysentery	Whole Plant	Paste
121	<i>Smilax zeylanica</i>	Smilacaceae	Firangi chettu	Climber	Paralysis	Tuber	Paste
122	<i>Solanum anguivi</i>	Solanaceae	Vakudu	Shrub	Pains	Leaf	Paste
					Scabies	Seed	Paste
					Tooth ache	Seed	Paste
123	<i>Soyimida febrifuga</i>	Meliaceae	Somid	Tree	Menstrual disorders	Stem bark	Decoction
124	<i>Spbaeranthus indicus</i>	Asteraceae	Boda taram	Herb	Impotency	Root	Powder
					Gastric trouble	Flower	Paste
125	<i>Spondias pinnata</i>	Anacardiaceae	Konda mamidi	Tree	Dysentery	Stem bark	Decoction
126	<i>Stemona tuberosa</i>	Stemonaceae	Tamalapak u dumpa	Climber	Dysentery	Root	Paste
					Fever	Tuber	Paste

127	<i>Sterculia urens</i>	Sterculiaceae	Kovela	Tree	Rheumatic pains	Stem bark	Paste
					Scorpion sting	Gum	Paste
128	<i>Strychnos nux-vomica</i>	Loganiaceae	Mushini	Tree	Scabies	Root bark	Paste
					Digestive disorders	Stem bark	Paste
129	<i>Strychnos potatorum</i>	Loganiaceae	Induba	Tree	Asthama	Stem	Devotion
					Dog bite	Seed	Paste
					Phlegm	Seed	Powder
130	<i>Syzygium cumini</i>	Myrtaceae	Neredu	Tree	Diabetes	Fruit	Powder
					Kidney stones	Seed	Powder
131	<i>Tephrosia villosa</i>	Fabaceae	Nugu vempali	Herb	Caries of teeth	Root	Paste
					Diabetes	Leaf	Juice
					Stomach pain	Root	Paste
132	<i>Terminalia alata</i>	Combretaceae	Nalla maddi	Tree	Dysentery	Stem bark	Powder
					Hemorrhoids	Stem bark	Powder
133	<i>Terminalia arjuna</i>	Combretaceae	Tella maddi	Tree	Diabetes	Stem bark	Paste
134	<i>Terminalia bellerica</i>	Combretaceae	Tanikaya	Tree	Antiemetics	Stem bark	Paste
					Asthma	Seed	Powder
					Skin diseases	Seed	Paste
					Diarrhea	Seed	Powder
135	<i>Terminalia chebula</i>	Combretaceae	Karakkaya	Tree	Cough	Fruit	Powder
					Dysentery	Fruit	Devotion
136	<i>Thespesia populnea</i>	Malvaceae	Ganga Raavi	Tree	Skin diseases	Leaf	Paste
					Dysentery	Stem bark	Devotion
137	<i>Tiliacora acuminata</i>	Menispermaceae	Teega mushini	Climber	Snake bite	Root	Paste
					Cough	Leaf	Paste
138	<i>Tinospora cordifolia</i>	Menispermaceae	Tippa teega	Climber	Bone fracture	Stem	Paste
					Cancer	Root	Paste
					Cuts	Stem	Paste
					Diabetes	Stem	Decoction
					Fever	Stem	Decoction
					Jaundice	Root	Paste

					Malaria	Root	Paste
					Snake bite	Root	Powder
139	<i>Toddalia asiatica</i>	Rutaceae	Varra kasintha'	Shrub	Snake and fox bites	Root bark	Paste
					Dyspepsia	Root bark	Paste
					Dysentery	Root	Juice
140	<i>Triantbema decandra</i>	Aizoaceae	Tella galijeru	Herb	Jaundice	Leaf	Paste
141	<i>Triantbema portulacastrum</i>	Aizoaceae	Galijeru	Herb	Bone fracture	Leaf	Paste
					kidney troubles	Leaf	Decoction
142	<i>Tribulus terrestris</i>	Zygophyllaceae	Palleru	Herb	Stomach pain	Root	Juice
					Wounds and Boils	Root	Paste
143	<i>Trichosanthes dioica</i>	Cucurbitaceae	Avuguda teega	Climber	Cough and Fever	Fruit	Paste
					Earache	Seed	Oil
144	<i>Vanda tessellata</i>	Orchidaceae	Sanna rastram	Herb	Bone fracture	Whole Plant	Paste
					Dyspepsia	Leaf	Paste
145	<i>Ventilago denticulata</i>	Rhamnaceae	Yerra chirathala	Climber	Chronic rheumatism	Stem bark	Paste
146	<i>Vetiveria zizanioides</i>	Poaceae	Vatti veru	Grass	Stomach pain	Root	Paste
					Ulcers in stomach	Root	Paste
147	<i>Vitex negundo</i>	Verbinaceae	Vavili	Tree	Cancer	Whole Plant	Powder
					Dyspepsia	Leaf	Juice
148	<i>Withania somnifera</i>	Solanaceae	Aswagandha	Shrub	Skin diseases	Leaf	Paste
					Galactagogue	Root	Powder
					Mental disorders	Whole Plant	Paste
149	<i>Woodfordia fruticosa</i>	Lythraceae	Jagipuvvulu	Shrub	Leprosy	Stem bark	Paste
150	<i>Wrightia arborea</i>	Apocynaceae	Tedla pala'	Tree	Snake bite	Latex	Milk
151	<i>Wrightia tinctoria</i>	Apocynaceae	Ankudu	Tree	Psoriasis	Leaf	Paste
152	<i>Xylia xylocarpa</i>	Mimosaceae	Konda tangedu	Tree	Gonorrhoea	Root bark	Paste

153	<i>Zanthoxylum armatum</i>	Rutaceae	Kasemi	Tree	Scabies	Leaf	Paste
154	<i>Zingiber zerumbet</i>	Zingiberaceae	Saluva dumpa	Herb	Fever	Rhizome	Paste
155	<i>Zizyphus mauritiana</i>	Rhamnaceae	Regu	Tree	Cooling effect	Fruit	Paste
					Diarrhoea	Fruit	Paste
156	<i>Zizyphus oenoplia</i>	Rhamnaceae	Parimi	Shrub	Blisters	Root	Paste
					Snake bite	Stem	Paste
					Tuberculosis	Stem	Decoction

Anogeissus acuminata

Anogeissus latifolia

Argyreia nervosa

Aristolochia bracteolata

Calotropis gigantea

Canavalia gladiata

Aerva lanata

Barringtonia acutangula

Careya arborea.

Gloriosa superba

Gmelina arborea

Glycosmis mauritiana

Rauwolfia serpentina

Vanda tessellata

Ventilago denticulate

Wrightia arborea

Xylocarpus xylocarpa

Bauhinia racemosa